

Identification of glutathione-S-transferase gene polymorphisms in type 2 diabetes mellitus patients attending Abdullahi Wase Specialist Hospital, Kano State Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

Glutathione-S-transferases (GSTs) are a family of antioxidant enzymes that include several classes with various polymorphisms. This work was aimed at investigating the association between the polymorphisms of the GSTT1 gene and type 2 diabetes mellitus (T2DM). The frequency of GSTT1 genotypes in T2DM patients and non-diabetic controls were studied. A total of 30 diagnosed cases of type 2 diabetes mellitus were selected from the diabetes clinic section of Abdullahi Wase Specialist Hospital, Kano Nigeria. A total of 30 non-diabetic individuals were also selected as control from the outpatient department (OPD) section of the hospital. All the subjects were assessed for fasting blood sugar (FBS), body mass index (BMI), Systolic and Diastolic Blood Pressures (SBP and DBP) and the genotypes of GSTT1 were determined using multiplex polymerase chain reaction (mPCR) techniques. FBS and BMI were significantly high ($P < 0.05$) in diabetics ($225.58 \pm 83.58 \text{ mg/dL}$ and $27.53 \pm 3.99 \text{ kg/m}^2$ respectively) as compared to the non-diabetic controls ($90.85 \pm 14.87 \text{ mg/dL}$ and $21.46 \pm 4.36 \text{ kg/m}^2$ respectively). There were no significant differences ($P < 0.05$) for SBP and DBP in the diabetics ($125.73 \pm 20.72 \text{ mmHg}$ and $85.83 \pm 13.65 \text{ mmHg}$ respectively) as compared to the non-diabetic controls ($117.33 \pm 3.04 \text{ mmHg}$ and $79.90 \pm 10.05 \text{ mmHg}$ respectively). This implies that the body weight of the diabetic patients is increased being a risk factor in diabetes mellitus. Furthermore, the GSST1 positive polymorphism was present in 95% of the samples analyzed (i.e. diabetics and controls). There was no presence of the deletion polymorphism in the two groups. This implies that there was no association of GSTT1 polymorphisms with T2DM in the studied population; Even though GSTT1 is associated with T2DM in other populations. Other polymorphisms of GST should be studied to ascertain their roles in the pathogenesis of T2DM in this population.

Keywords Glutathione-S-transferase (GSTT1), Type 2 diabetes mellitus, Gene polymorphism, Multiplex PCR

1. Introduction

Complexation in solutions in multi systems metal cation–EDTA–secondary ligand (amines, amino acids, dicarboxylic diabetes mellitus (DM) is a non-communicable metabolic disease. It is caused by lack of adequate production of Insulin (i.e. Type 1 DM) by the β cells of the pancreas. It is called type 2 diabetes mellitus if the target cells for insulin action are resistant to it even when it is adequately produced. More than 16 million people have diabetes in Africa. By 2045 this figure is estimated to rise up to 41 million [1]. Oxidative stress is defined in general as excess formation and/or insufficient removal of highly reactive molecules such as reactive oxygen species (ROS) [2]. Pancreatic β -cells have emerged as a putative target of oxidative stress-induced tissue damage, and this seems to explain in part the progressive deterioration of β -cell function in type 2 diabetes mellitus (T2DM) [3].

Endogenous antioxidant enzymes exist to inactivate ROS. One of these enzymes is glutathione-S-transferase (GST), which carries out a wide range of functions in cells: removal of ROS, regeneration of S-thiolated protein (as consequences of oxidative stress) and conjugation with endogenous ligands, as well as reactions in metabolic pathways not associated with detoxification [4]. As a phase II biotransformation enzyme, GST catalyzes the conjugation of reduced glutathione (GSH) to electrophilic centers on a wide range of substrates [5].

In humans, glutathione-S-transferases supergene family (GST; EC 2.5.1.18) have been assigned to at least eight separate classes designated alpha (A), mu (M), kappa (K), omega(O), pi (P), sigma (S), theta (T) and zeta (Z), which are encoded by the GSTA, GSTM, GSTK, GSTO, GSTP, GSTS, GSTT, and GSTZ genes, respectively [6].

Several GST polymorphisms have been associated with an increased or decreased susceptibility to several diseases. Deletion polymorphisms in the GSTT1 gene, as an important member of the GST family, result in complete lack of GSTT1 protein [7]. The GSTT1 null genotype has been shown to be a genetic risk factor for the development of type 2 diabetes and its cardiovascular complications in Scotland population [8], in Japanese population [9], and in Egyptian populations [10]. This present study seeks investigate the association between GSTT1 gene polymorphisms and type 2 diabetes mellitus in patients attending Abdullahi Wase Specialist Hospital, Kano.

2. Materials and method

2.1. Patient selection

A total of 30 blood samples from T2DM patients (15 males and 15 females) and 30 non-diabetic controls (15 males and 15 females) were collected from Abdullahi Wase Specialist Hospital (AWSH). Written informed consent was obtained from all the participants. Data collection was done for each patient on demographic and clinical variables including age, alcohol consumption, body mass index (BMI), height, weight, cigarette smoking, and family history. Patients with overnight fasting plasma glucose of more than 126.0 mg/dL and were already diagnosed by the hospital as diabetics were included in the T2DM category. Participants having a fasting blood glucose level below 110.0 mg/dL without a family history of diabetes were included in the study as controls. Ethical Committee approval was obtained from the ethical and research committee of the Kano State ministry of health, prior to the recruitment of subjects in this study.

2.2. Biochemical and clinical estimations

The BMI were calculated according to Quetelet equation by using weight in kg, height in m^2 . Fasting plasma glucose was also determined using glucometer (OKmeter LUMINA, OK-14V, Taiwan). Systolic and Diastolic blood pressures were also determined using a clinical mercury manometer (S.H.M. Shenghai, China).

2.3. DNA extraction

Peripheral blood (5 mL) was collected from all the subjects in sample tubes with EDTA as anticoagulant. Genomic DNA was extracted from the whole blood using a standard blood genomic extraction kit (Dongsheng Biotech) in the following protocol as stated in the manual accompanying the kit.

To a 1.5 ml micro-centrifuge tube, 400 μ l anti-coagulated blood was added and 2 volume of solution RS was added to the tube. The tube was mixed thoroughly by vortexing. This was then centrifuged for 3 minutes at 5000 rpm. The supernatant was discarded. To the residue in the tube 200 μ l solution DS was added. The mixture was then mixed thoroughly by vortexing to yield a homogenous solution. To the homogenous solution, 20 μ l Proteinase K and 220 μ l Solution MS were added and mixed thoroughly by vortexing. The mixture was incubated at 65 °C for 10 min to yield a homogeneous solution.

After incubation, 220 μ l ethanol (96 –100%) was added to the sample and vortexed. The mixture was then pipetted into a spin column placed on a 2 ml collection tube and then centrifuged at 12,000 rpm for 1 minute. The flow through was discarded. To the spin column, 500 μ l of wash buffer called solution PS was added and centrifuged for 1 minute at 12,000 rpm and the flow through was discarded. Another 500 μ l of a second wash buffer called solution PE was added and centrifuged for 1 minute at 12,000 rpm and the flow through was discarded. This step was repeated ones more.

It was then centrifuged for 3 minutes at 12,000 rpm to dry the column membrane. The flow through and the collection tube were discarded. The spin column was then placed in a clean 1.5 ml micro-centrifuge tube and 60 μ l deionized water

(PH = 8.0) was added. The mixture from step 8 was then centrifuged for 2 minutes at 12,000 rpm to elute the DNA. The yielded genomic DNA was then stored at -20 °C.

2.4. Polymerase chain reaction analysis

A total number of 60 individuals (30 T2DM patients and 30 healthy volunteers) were recruited for this study. All the T2DM patients and the healthy control were genotyped for the GSSTT1 gene polymorphism. The screening was done using multiplex PCR. This is because β -globin gene was also amplified to serve as an internal control in this work. The duration of the disease in all the diabetic cases varies from one year to fifteen years.

GSTT1 genetic polymorphisms were evaluated using a multiplex polymerase chain reaction (PCR) technique (MJ Mini Thermal Cycler; Bio-Rad Laboratories, Hercules, CA, USA). The PCR primers were ordered for and synthesized from a commercial company (Eurofin Genomics). The PCR was carried out in a total volume of 15 μ L containing 1.5 μ L of 10taq BufferA, 0.51 μ L of each primer (Forward and reverse GSTT1 and forward and reverse β -Globin), 0.75 μ L of MgCl₂, 0.13 μ L of deoxynucleotide triphosphates (Mix), 0.13 μ L of KAPAtaq polymerase, 1 μ L of genomic DNA and 9.45 μ L double deionized water. Amplification was performed by initial denaturation at 94 °C for 5 min., followed by 30 cycles at 94 °C for 1 min., 64 °C for 1 min. and 72 °C for 1 min., and a final extension of 72 °C for 7 min. This is as summarized in the Table below:

Genes	Primers	Cycler condition
GSTT1	Forward:	No. of cycles: 35cycles
	5'-TTCCTTACTGGTCCTCACATCTC-3'	Initial Denaturation: 95°C-3min
	Reverse:	Denaturation: 94°C-30sec
	5'-TCACGGGATCATGGCCAGCA-3'	Annealing: 60°C-30sec
B-Globin	Forward:	Extension: 72°C-1min
	5'-CAACTTCATCCACGTTTACC-3'	Final elongation: 72°C-10min
	Reverse:	
	5'-GAAGAGCCAAGGACAGGTAC-3'	

2.5. Agarose gel electrophoresis

The amplified products were identified by electrophoresis in the following steps:

To prepare 2% agarose gel, 2 g of agarose salt was weighed into a conical flask. To the salt, 80 ml Tris acetate EDTA buffer was added to the gel and mixed thoroughly. The mixture was then microwaved for 5 minutes. This is then cooled in water at room temperature. After cooling, 4 μ L of Ethidium bromide dye was added and shaken thoroughly. The gel was then casted on the cartridge and allowed to solidify. A mixture of 2 μ L loading dye and 4 μ L of the PCR products were loaded in the gel well and the gel was set to run at 110 volt for 35 minutes.

2.6. Statistical analysis

All the figures were presented as mean \pm standard deviation (SD). The data were compared between patients and controls using the Student's *t*-test for normally-distributed variables. All statistical tests were performed using the statistical package for the social sciences, version 20.0 software (SPSS 20.0).

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Results

Results of FBS, BMI, SBP, DBP, were presented in Table 1. From the result, FBS and BMI were found to be significantly higher in the diabetic compared to the apparently healthy control ($p < 0.05$). There was no significant difference found in the SBP and DBP of the diabetics when compared with the controls.

Table 1 Mean FBS, BMI, blood pressures (Systolic BP and Diastolic BP) in diabetic and control subjects.

Subjects	FBS(mg/dL)	BMI(kg/m ²)	Systolic BP(mmHg)	Diastolic BP(mmHg)
Diabetics n = 30	225.58 \pm 83.51 ^a	27.53 \pm 3.99 ^a	125.73 \pm 20.72	85.83 \pm 13.65
Controls n = 30	90.85 \pm 14.87 ^b	21.46 \pm 4.36 ^b	117.23 \pm 3.04	79.90 \pm 10.05

Data were reported as means \pm Standard deviation. Values with different superscripts down the column show significant difference at $P < 0.05$. **FBS**: Fasting Blood Sugar; **BMI**: Body mass Index; **BP**: Blood Pressure.

The result of all the parameters, FBS, BMI, SBP, DBP according to sex were presented in Table 2. The result shows that FBS and BMI are significantly higher in male diabetics compared to male control ($P < 0.05$) and no significant difference ($P < 0.05$) between the male diabetics and male controls for SBP and the DBP. The result also shows significantly higher FBS and BMI in female diabetics compared to female controls ($P < 0.05$) and no significant difference between the female diabetics and female controls for SBP and the DBP ($P < 0.05$).

Table 2 Mean FBS, BMI, Blood pressures (Systolic BP and Diastolic BP) values of subjects according to sex.

Subjects	Gender	FBS (mg/dL)	BMI (kg/m ²)	Systolic BP (mmHg)	Diastolic BP (mmHg)
Diabetics n = 30	Male N = 15	215.53±84.90 ^a	26.36±3.79 ^a	129.73±18.88	86.33±13.69
	Female N = 15	235.63±83.76 ^a	28.68±3.97 ^a	122.00±22.42	81.67±8.79
Controls n = 30	Male N = 15	97.28±13.10 ^b	22.08±3.44 ^b	117.87±13.47	80.47±11.85
	Female N = 15	80.43±14.06 ^b	20.48±5.19 ^b	111.73±13.94	76.93±7.67

Data were reported as means ± Standard deviation. Values with different superscripts down the column show significant difference at $P < 0.05$. **FBS:** Fasting Blood Sugar; **BMI:** Body mass Index; **BP:** Blood Pressure.

The results of PCR for the identification of GSTT1 polymorphisms show that the GSTT1 positive polymorphism was identified in the 95% of the participants (i.e. both the diabetic and control samples and that 5% of the participant failed to amplify and 0% null genotype (deletion polymorphism) was identified. The results showed no significant difference ($P < 0.05$) between the T2DM patients and the controls.

Figure 1 PCR products analyzed on 2% agarose gel. The presence (positive) and absence (null) of GSTT1 was detected by the presence or absence of a band at 480bp (corresponding to GSTT1). β -Globin is considered as internal control (260bp). 1000bp DNA ladder. Lanes 1-11; GSTT1 positive genotype (Lane 1-11 male diabetics).

Figure 2 PCR products analyzed on 2% agarose gel. The presence (positive) and absence (null) of GSTT1 was detected by the presence or absence of a band at 480bp (corresponding to GSTT1). β -Globin is considered as internal control (260bp). 1000 bp DNA ladder. Lanes 1-11; GSTT1 positive genotype (Lane 1-11 male control).

The results of the frequencies of the GSTT1 gene polymorphisms and the failed samples were presented in Table 3. The results show 95% of the positive polymorphism, 0% of the null polymorphism and 5% of failed samples.

Table 3 Frequencies of the GSTT1 gene polymorphisms and failed samples.

Polymorphisms	Frequency (%)
GSTT1 Positive	95
GSTT1 Null	0
Failed	5

3.2. Discussion

The FBS, BMI, Systolic BP and Diastolic BP of all the diabetics and the controls were determined in this study. The results showed a significant difference ($P < 0.05$) between the diabetics and the controls for FBS and BMI. This is in agreement with the finding of Amer *et al* [1] who found significant difference ($P < 0.05$) for these parameters in comparing diabetics with controls. This finding negates the work of Moasser *et al* [10] who found no significant difference ($P < 0.05$) between the BMI of the diabetic patients and those of the controls in an Iranian population. Although the mean SBP and DBP are higher in the diabetics (129.73 ± 18.88 and 86.33 ± 13.69 respectively) compared to the controls (117.87 ± 13.47 and 80.47 ± 11.85 respectively), there were no significant differences ($P < 0.05$). This is in contrast to the findings of Amer *et al* [1]. This may be explained in part by the fact that majority of diabetic participants were placed on antihypertensive drugs which they complied to religiously. This may be one among many reasons why these parameters are relative comparable to those of non-diabetic controls.

The gender was also separately compared in this study. Male diabetics with the male controls only were compared as well as female diabetics with female controls. The result was similar to the first comparison. The mean FBS and BMI of the male diabetics (215.53 ± 84.90 and 26.36 ± 3.79 respectively) showed significant differences ($p < 0.05$) as compared to those of male controls (97.28 ± 13.10 and 22.08 ± 3.44 respectively). The mean FBS and BMI of the female diabetics (235.63 ± 83.76 and 28.68 ± 3.97 respectively) showed significant differences ($p < 0.05$) as compared to those of female controls (80.43 ± 14.06 and 20.48 ± 5.19 respectively). These findings corroborated the findings of Qianqian *et al* [11]. They worked with a Chinese population and their findings revealed significance differences ($p < 0.05$) in the BMI and FBS of the patients compared to the controls. The findings in this study however, are in contrast with the Moasser *et al* [10] who found no significant difference between the BMI of the diabetics and the controls in an Iranian population. These differences in the result may be attributed to the genetic variability in the different population studied.

Figures 1 and 2 represent the results of the GSTT1 genotyping. The result showed no association between GSTT1 polymorphism and Diabetes mellitus (95% positive GSTT1 genotype and 0% null genotype for both diabetics and control groups) in this part of the world. This is close to the findings of Raza *et al* [4] who worked with 198 diabetic and non-diabetic (control) participants. In their results they found 93.9% positive GSTT1 genotype and only 6.1% null GSTT1 genotype. This indicates that the frequencies of the positive polymorphisms are very high in the two populations. Differences in the result obtained by Raza *et al* [4] and this result might be due to difference in the ethnic, genetic and environmental background of the populations studied.

Zaki *et al* [12] undertook a study on An Egyptian Type 2 diabetic patients investigating the polymorphisms of GSTT1, GSTM1 and GSTP1 and the risk of developing the disease. They found out that GSTT1 null genotype polymorphism did not show significant difference ($p < 0.05$) between the control group and diabetic cases. This is also in line with findings obtained in this work. Gonul *et al* [13] also conducted similar studies on a Turkish T2DM patients and their findings revealed no significant difference ($p < 0.05$) between GSTT1 (both null and positive genotypes) and T2DM. They however observed significant differences ($p < 0.05$) in the combined effect of GSTM1 null and OGG1 (8-oxoguanine-DNA glycosylase 1) variant genotypes, in GSTM1 null, in the combined effect of GSTT1 null and OGG1 in the diabetic patients as compared to control. This finding suggest that similar results may have been obtained in this study, if other polymorphisms like GSTM1 and GSTP1 would have been analyzed together with GSTT1 polymorphism. Similar studies by Moasser *et al* [10] with an Iranian population also agreed with the findings in this work (i.e. there is no significant differences in the frequency of GSTT1 genotypes between the diabetics and the control). Although they too found significant difference when both GSTM1 and GSTT1 null genotypes were combined (19.88% in patients against 11.83% in the controls, $p < 0.05$).

The results of this study opposed the studies of Chinese (Wang *et al*) [14], Indian (Ramprasath *et al*) [15], Egyptian (Amer *et al*) [1] and Brazillian (Pinheiro *et al*) [16] researchers who observed that the prevalence of GSTT1 genotypes is associated with the development of type 2 diabetic mellitus. Ramprasath *et al* [15] studied a South Indian T2DM patient. Their findings showed significant associations between T2DM and null genotype of GSTT1. Amer *et al* [1], also

indicated that the GSTT1 and GSTM1 distributions significantly differ between T2DM patients and controls in an Egyptian population. Wang *et al* [14] performed a study on Chinese T2DM patients investigating the polymorphism of GSTT1. They found that the GSTT1 null genotype was observed in 61% of patients against 51% of controls. Their studies suggest that the GSTT1 null genotype contribute to the development of T2DM. All these deviations from this present study could be in part is attributed to differences in the populations in terms of genetic variability.

4. Conclusion

The results showed that body weight is higher significantly ($p < 0.05$) in the diabetic patients than in the non-diabetic controls and no significant difference ($p < 0.05$) in their blood pressures was found. The findings here, also showed no association between GSTT1 polymorphism and type 2 diabetes mellitus in the population studied. The result thus shows that absence of GSTT1 gene polymorphism may not be a factor in the pathogenesis of T2DM in the population studied.

Conflict of Interest

The authors of this article declare no conflict of interest.

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